

ON THE INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF
TRANSFORMATION AND DERIVATION

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Abstract

This report describes some of the cases in which the concepts of transformation and derivation have been studied. The role of the study of these states in the study of static and dynamic states of language is revealed.

Key words and expressions: language, transformation, derivation, static state, dynamic state.

Трансформация ва деривация тушунчалари талқинига доир

Аннотация

Ушбу маърузада трансформация ва деривация тушунчаларининг ўрганилишига доир айрим ҳолатлар баён қилинган. Ушбу ҳолатлар ўрганилишининг тилнинг статик ва динамик ҳолатлари тадқиқидаги ўрни очиқ берилган.

Таянч сўз ва иборалар: тил, трансформация, деривация, статик ҳолат, динамик ҳолат.

О толковании понятий трансформации и деривации

Аннотация

В настоящем докладе изложены некоторые аспекты изучения концепций трансформации и деривации. Изучение этих случаев выявило роль данных понятий изучения статического и динамического состояния языка.

Опорные слова и выражения: язык, трансформация, деривация, статическое состояние, динамическое состояние.

V.S Khrakovsky means transformation, the expression of a certain semantic state in the language in one way or another, and derivation means the transfer of one semantic state to another. In this case, of course, the commonality of meaning between the main sentence and the derivative sentence is avoided. V.S Khrakovsky gives the following example: Таня открывает окно - Бабушка заставила Таню открыть окно (Tanya opens the window - * -Grandma forced Tanya to open the window); Ребёнок спит —► Ребёнок хочет спать (The child is asleep - + The child wants to sleep) [4, p. 493].

The concept of derivation was actually introduced by the Polish scientist Eji Kurilovich. His article *Реруа (Derivation lexicque et derivation syntaxique)* ("Lexical Derivation and Syntactic Derivation") was written in the 1930s, and the concept of derivation was known to us through it. In particular, the translation of this article into Russian has become a major event in our linguistics.

Nji Kurilovich explains both lexical derivation and syntactic derivation in the example of words: камень (stone) * каменьщик (tot teruvchi); каменный (pinali). The scientist states that the first example is an example of lexical derivation, and the second example is an example of I grammtactic derivation) [S.263]. In the first example, a new word is not formed, and in the second example, the syntactic function of the word's is changed.

It should be noted that Eji Kurilovich's derivation theory has been creatively developed by linguists in recent years. In particular, Russian linguists (L.N. Murzin, V.S. Khrakovsky, E.S. Kubryakova, Yu.D. Apresyan, I.P. Raspopov, S.N. Sichyova) made a worthy contribution.

In Russian linguistics, serious attention has been paid to the study of the phenomenon of syntactic derivation, and as a result, various methods of analysis have been introduced. We observe this more closely in L.N. Murzin's research. This is natural, of course. After all, L.N. Murzin is the founder of world derivatology. It was through his efforts that in 1981 a scientific conference on "Theoretical Problems of Derivatology" was organized at the University of Perm, where the term derivatology was first introduced.

Researcher F.Ibragimova emphasizes that the phenomenon of austerity is inextricably linked with the concept of austerity: Excessive speech occurs for a variety of reasons. In linguistics, the phenomenon of privilege is considered as a counter-movement that is not achieved in austerity ") [1, p. 32].

A text with a plus sign, according to L.N. Murzin, always needs to be shortened. As a result, a compression phenomenon occurs. Thus, the loss of privilege from the text is considered compression) [3, p. 75].

However, the author considers syntactic derivation to be the formal reduction of a sentence by the loss of precedence in the text. In this case, the transformation becomes the working mechanism of syntactic derivation.

The change and construction of language units is its dynamic state, which is the opposite of statics. Dynamic and static state is a form of survival and development of any language.

Therefore, as important as the study of the static state of language is, so important is the study of the dynamic state.

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